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Artificial Intelligence (AI) and “Agrivangelism”: Leveraging Technology for Agricultural Evangelism towards Poverty Alleviation in Nigeria

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Abstract

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is widely employed in the agricultural field to improve yields, efficiency, and profitability and develop economic forecasts. With the great commission of evangelising the whole world with the good news of salvation, one of the challenges encountered from one culture to the other is poverty amongst the rural communities whose main occupation is agriculture. However, these rural dwellers face different challenges, including insecurity and poor infrastructure. There is a need to identify with these poor agrarian communities. There is a need for mission agencies to leverage AI in agriculture to reach them with the gospel. This paper examined the conceptual overviews of AI and “Agrivangelism,” established the relationship between AI, agriculture, and poverty alleviation, and drew out implications for “Agrivangelism”. These findings were deduced from the materials reviewed on leveraging AI in agriculture: farm monitoring; plant disease and insect detection; intelligent farm chemicals application; weeding; aerial survey and imaging; produce grading and sorting; ploughing, planting and other field operations; automation of irrigation; AI for livestock, fish and poultry farming; traceability and supply chain management–blockchain technology; farm management; optimisation of farming operations and decisions; and finding market opportunities for farmers. These findings and implications were discussed within the purview of Divine Command Theory towards leveraging AI in agriculture. The following implications were drawn for mission agencies towards effective “Agrivangelism”: holistic ministry, community engagement, leveraging human resources, partnership with government or private agencies, and funding.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence (AI), Agriculture, “Agrivangelism”, Poverty Alleviation, Divine Command Theory

Introduction

The most complete term to describe how domestic animals and crop plants provide food and other items to support the world's population is agriculture¹. Agriculture is the basis for the sustainability of any economy. It plays a vital role in long-term economic growth and structural change². Over the years, agriculture has proven to be a steadfast source of income worldwide, satisfying humanity's most essential need which is food. However, despite the global need for food, hunger remains an enduring issue because the agricultural sector is facing myriads of challenges, especially in developed countries which include Nigeria³. In the past, agricultural activities were limited to food and crop production. However, in the last two decades, it has evolved into processing, producing, marketing, and distributing crops and livestock products. With the rise of the global geometric population, it becomes imperative that agricultural practices are reviewed to provide innovative approaches to sustaining and improving agricultural activities⁴.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is widely employed in agriculture to improve yield, efficiency and profitability and develop economic forecasts⁵. In many parts of the world, AI is being deployed in the agricultural sector, and dramatic transformation has been observed in many in agricultural sector across the globe⁶. The application of artificial intelligence (AI) into agriculture will be facilitated by various technical advancements, such as big data analytics, robotics, the Internet of Things, low-cost sensors and cameras, drone technology, and even widespread internet access on geographically separated farms⁷. In order to increase crop yields and decrease water usage, fertilisers, and pesticides, Artificial Intelligence (AI) systems will be able to anticipate which crop to grow in a given year and when the ideal dates to sow and harvest are in a particular area. These insights will be gained by examining soil management data sources like temperature, precipitation, soil analysis, moisture content, and past crop performance⁷. This will help to reduce the impact of fertilisers and pesticides on natural ecosystems using AI technologies. It will also help to increase worker's safety, keeping food prices down and ensuring that food production keeps pace with the increasing population⁷.

With the great commission of evangelising the whole world with the good news of salvation, one of the challenges encountered from one culture to the other is poverty amongst the rural communities whose main occupation is agriculture. However, these rural dwellers face different challenges, including insecurity and poor infrastructure. There is a need to identify with these agrarian communities and find ways to help them overcome some of the challenges as this will help reach them with the gospel. AI can be a powerful instrument for evangelisation among rural populations in the age of globalisation. It can help alleviate poverty and address some of these people's issues. This paper aims to present the conceptual overviews of AI and "Agrivangelism", establish the relationship between AI, agriculture, and poverty alleviation, and draw out implications for "Agrivangelism". This paper is silent on the methodology used. There is no research work without using a particular methodology.

Conceptual Overviews

1. Overview of the Concept of AI

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has been a technological tool in various sectors, with its roots deeply embedded in mathematics, computer science, and engineering. This technology simulates human intelligence and encompasses learning, reasoning, problem-solving, and language comprehension capabilities⁸. Among the many subsets of AI, Machine Learning (ML) and Computer Vision stand out prominently⁸. ML is used to create statistical models and algorithms that let computers carry out particular tasks without explicit programming⁸. It emphasises the ability of machines to learn from experience and adapt to new information⁹.

Another specialised area of artificial intelligence is computer vision, which teaches machines to comprehend and decide based on visual information from the outside world¹⁰. It automatically extracts, analyses, and comprehends relevant data from a single image or a series of photos. Computer vision mimics human vision to allow machines to recognise and process things in photos and videos, similarly to human vision, but with incredible speed and accuracy. Computer vision techniques include motion estimation, pattern recognition, object recognition, and image segmentation¹¹. Generally, AI techniques simulate human intelligence and rely heavily on machine learning (ML) for most applications¹². The fundamental elements of artificial intelligence encompass machine learning, natural language processing, computer vision, robotics, and expert systems¹³. The agricultural sector holds immense significance, with a global value of \$3.6 trillion and a consistent contribution of 4% to the global GDP¹⁴. However, it faces severe obstacles, including unpredictability in weather, pests and illnesses that damage crops and the adverse effects of desertification and climate change¹⁴. To solve these severe obstacles, technology, digitalisation, and AI are potential solutions to these challenges¹⁵. The integration of AI in agriculture aims to address these challenges, enhance productivity, and reduce

human effort¹⁶. The strategic role of AI in agriculture becomes apparent, considering its potential to reshape existing methodologies and technologies for maximising crop yield and ensuring sustainable food production¹⁴. Hence, sustainability remains a pivotal theme in this context, with AI-driven solutions showing promise in supporting environmentally friendly practices¹⁴.

Moreover, stakeholders in the food and agricultural sector face the challenge of optimising their operations to minimise losses and costs while maximising yields¹⁷. Therefore, the infusion of AI, especially Machine Learning and Computer Vision, is innovative and transformative. This integration reshapes the methodologies and operations of farmers and agricultural stakeholders, often called Agri Tech⁸. The numerous benefits range from enhanced efficiency to increased profitability and sustainability⁸. This also includes Computer Vision which aids in detecting crop diseases and pests early to ensure timely interventions as well as predictive analytics which is an advantage of Machine Learning to forecasts yields, considering various determinants like weather patterns and soil quality⁸. The advent of AI-powered robotics is diminishing the reliance on manual labour, while AI's ability in data analytics is streamlining supply chains. Furthermore, AI's intelligent management of resources is a significant stride toward environmental sustainability in agriculture⁸.

AI's ability to perform intelligent tasks opens opportunities to improve current agricultural practices by (i) providing support services previously deemed too resource-intensive, expensive, or unavailable (e.g. due to lack of skills and expertise among local professionals); and (ii) reducing current operational costs by saving time and labour performed by agriculture workers. Today, AI is considered one of the most potent solutions to the many challenges the agricultural sector faces in low- and high-income countries⁸. AI has entered agriculture and provides cutting-edge technology with applications throughout the food system, including production, distribution, consumption and harvest yield uncertainty⁸.

The latest technologies of automated systems using agricultural robots and drones have made a tremendous contribution to the agro-based sector. Various hi-tech computer-based systems are designed to determine vital parameters like weed detection, yield detection, crop quality, and many other techniques⁶. While the swift progress within the AI domain might instill concerns about job displacement in more developed nations, it holds the potential to be viewed as a promising opportunity for developing countries¹⁸.

2. Overview of the Concept of "Agrivangelism"

"Agrivangelism" is a term coined by one of the writers of this paper based on the words "agriculture and evangelism." The idea came in one of the evangelism outreaches in 2022 to one of the agrarian communities called Ogbin in the Asa Local Government Area of Kwara State, which shares a border with the Orire Local Government Area of Oyo State. The idea was that if the church could partner with professionals to provide modern training for the poor farmers, it would go a long way in boosting their agricultural production, contribute towards poverty alleviation and be an avenue for the evangelistic effort to be fruitful for a holistic salvation experience.

Narratives of missionary group experiences are commonplace in many missionary endeavours. In Guatemala's poorest province, evangelical missionaries began to reach out to unreachable agricultural communities. They travelled there in order to start churches and evangelise. In one of the poorest countries in the Americas, the Pokomchi people with whom they were working were the poorest in the poorest province. A large number of people accepted Christ. Churches were established¹⁹. By mission standards, the task was done. The missionaries moved on to other communities. However, in one sense, little had changed. This story is replicated all over the world¹⁹. Well-meaning Christians work in missions and private voluntary organisations to bring hope and help to poor agriculturists worldwide. These farmers are usually physically and economically poor and often social outcasts with little hope¹⁹.

Mission agencies operate from the paradigm separating the spiritual from the physical; such have brought a "spiritual" solution, the "narrow Gospel of salvation." The Christ-motivated development workers, operating from the secular paradigm of the modern development industry, have brought a "physical" solution, technical knowledge and outside financial resources but little transformation of human life and communities¹⁹. There can never be a comprehensive solution to a comprehensive problem based on inadequate paradigms and piecemeal methodologies if there will be a holistic transformation in the lives of impoverished farmers. In that case, missionaries and Christian agricultural extension workers must synergise with a view towards the salvation of their souls and poverty alleviation.

Therefore, the concept of "Agrivangelism" is reaching out to agrarian communities with the gospel and, at the same time, providing necessary professional/technical support to them that would aid them in their chosen field, thereby leading to poverty alleviation. "Agrivangelism" is in tandem with Jesus' teaching in Matthew 25:35-40. The holistic gospel is what the early missionaries did; they preached the word of God and provided schools and hospitals. Contemporary missionaries need to take cues from early missionaries by leveraging AI to help poor farmers in rural areas.

Theoretical Review

This research adopts The Divine Command Theory to serve as the theoretical framework for this study. This theory is rooted in the philosophy of Thomas Aquinas, which states that man does not have a sense of moral right or wrong independent of God; for a man to identify or distinguish moral right from moral wrong, it is expected of him to know God's will²⁰. Furthermore, the theory states that the ethically correct course of action is what God requires or commands, and morality is ultimately founded on God's character or instructions. Hence, conduct is based on what is understood to be God's will; what makes actions right or wrong is what is scripturally right or wrong²¹.

The theory claims morality is ultimately based on God's commands or character and can be measured by obedience to God's command. This means that morality is ultimately based on God's commands or character and that the morally right action is what God commands or requires²². Furthermore, this theory relates to poverty reduction mainly through its ethical framework that focuses on following God's commands, including caring for the poor. This is also in line with the goal of historical and contemporary philosophers, which is to uphold theistic-based ethical views²².

The Biblical stance has been on caring for the poor in the society. From the Old Testament, the vulnerable in the society, the poor, widows and orphans are enjoined to be provided for as a religious duty. In the New Testament, Jesus took care of the poor. Many of the teachings of Jesus centre on the need to care for poor people. The early disciples in Acts of Apostles display their fulfilment of this mandate by going all out to take care of those in needs amongst them. By implication, since poverty reduction is in line with the mind of God as enshrined in the Holy Bible, it is a divine command.

The contemporary church should imbibe this trend taught and exemplified by Jesus and follow the early disciples' example of reaching out to the downtrodden amongst them. Many of these groups of people are found among the farmers in rural communities. Christian evangelistic efforts should be geared towards ministering holistically to them by helping them be more productive in their chosen field of agriculture through AI. The deployment of AI will increase productivity, contributing to a positive change in their economic status. This is the main essence of "agrivangelism", which uses the instrumentality of productive agricultural support to win souls for Christ which will also contribute immensely to poverty alleviation.

AI, Agriculture and Poverty Alleviation

1. Farm Monitoring

The success of the farm enterprise is wholly based on the end yield and the market rate. Crop yield depends on timely monitoring and scientific prescription of appropriate remedies²³. During the production season, visual indicators of crop growth and their respective geographic locations are occasionally required. Data extraction and analysis may be done precisely with monitoring systems that are based on AI and the Internet of Things (IoT). An IoT-based monitoring system tracks how various environmental factors, such as humidity, temperature, soil temperature, moisture content, and light intensity, affect plant growth²⁴. AI furnishes a precise way to monitor the crop and predict the yield automatically. Robots, enabled by AI, have been employed to monitor respiration, photosynthetic activity, yield and other biological factors. They have also been employed in pollution monitoring, measuring carbon dioxide and nitrous oxide emissions so farmers can reduce their environmental footprint¹².

2. *Plant's Disease and Insect Detection*

The loss of productivity can be prevented by persistently checking for plant illnesses and insect pests⁵. Plant disease monitoring by hand is time-consuming and prone to mistakes. AI and computer vision can be used to detect plant illnesses early on, reducing their negative consequences and overcoming the limitations of ongoing human surveillance²⁵. Plant Disease detection systems use various sensors to collect plant-related data in images at different intervals²⁶.

3. *Intelligent Farm Chemicals Application*

Even though weeds and pests are usually dispersed randomly or patchily, most traditional sprayers administer agrochemicals consistently, which wastes valuable compounds and increases expenses. It also increases the danger of crop damage, pest resistance to chemicals, pollution of the environment, and product contamination²⁷. Smart sprayers utilising machine vision and artificial intelligence are essential to distinguish target pests or weeds from non-target objects (e.g., vegetable crops) and precisely spray on the desired target/location²⁸. Detection of unwanted pests on crops, or weed detection, is implemented with frame-capturing drones and deep learning methods²⁹. Weeding is a very labour-intensive and costly farm activity in Nigeria. Reducing the physical hardship, cost, and time spent on such activities will increase the overall land yield and the losses due to crop failure. Some robots can autonomously navigate a farm and deliver targeted sprays of herbicides to help eliminate weeds; some crop-dusting robots also apply other agrochemicals³⁰.

4. *Weeding*

Weeds are unwanted plants that grow on farmlands and compete with crops for nutrients, space, and sunlight. If not removed, they obstruct crop growth, causing a reduction in crop yield and, consequently, in profit for farmers³¹. Weed control robots are designed based on real-time image detection as the early identification and control of weeds is paramount. Developing a visual method of discriminating between crop seedlings and weeds is essential to automating non-chemical weed control systems in agriculture and reducing chemical use through spot spraying³². These effectively save efforts while reducing environmental pollution caused by pesticide use³³.

5. *Aerial Survey and Imaging*

Unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), another name for drones, are primarily used in the military, business, and other specialised fields. But in the last 20 years, as information technology and sensor technologies have advanced, drone applications have expanded to include agriculture³⁴. Drone and global positioning systems (GPS) technology gives agriculture a high-tech makeover. Drones have been helpful in the field, soil analysis and land management, planting, crop spraying/fertilizer application, farm

monitoring/surveillance/health assessment, crop yield prediction, etc.³⁵. Drones have aided irrigation by identifying dry areas and areas needing improvement⁶.

6. Produce Grading and Sorting

Agricultural produce is graded based on its dimensions and other attributes. This grade is used to sort and assign them to different classes and sometimes to different sales channels. Visual inspection techniques have recently replaced the human eye due to the development of image processing algorithms. These algorithms can detect several faults that humans cannot notice at faster speeds³⁶. Compared to classic visual analysis algorithms, the new generation of intelligent grading and sorting algorithms is significantly more potent since they provide automated learning capabilities that guarantee detection performance far above the speed and accuracy of any experienced operator. There are sorting and grading systems for eggs, tomatoes, mangoes and garlic¹².

7. Ploughing, Planting and Other Field Operations

GPS-enabled, Tele-operated, and autonomous tractors and harvesters have also hit the markets³⁷. With advanced GPS, a tractor operator can tell which rows have been planted to avoid overlap, ensuring every seed is in the right place, with the depth, soil contact, and spacing needed to grow into a food-producing crop³⁸. GPS-enabled self-driving tractors and self-propelled equipment confer additional accuracy to the farming operation³⁹. Seed-planting robots are intelligent machines that automatically navigate an agricultural region and scatter seeds throughout a pre-drawn map. For quicker harvesting, robotic fruit and vegetable pickers can operate nonstop¹².

Compared to human labour, these robots can gather crops more quickly and in more significant quantities.

8. Automation of Irrigation

The development of agriculture and productive farming has always been closely correlated with the efficient use of water through irrigation⁴⁰. AI analysis of plant behaviour is a powerful tool that allows irrigation fine-tuning. Automatic plant irrigators are planted on the field through wireless technology for drip irrigation¹². Timely prediction of irrigation requirements and crop yields is necessary for farmer's welfare and satisfaction. The beforehand prediction significantly contributes to minimising production costs and maximising crop yields⁴¹.

9. AI for Livestock, Fish and Poultry Farming

AI helps livestock farms accumulate and analyse data to predict consumer behaviour, like buying patterns, leading trends, etc⁴². In terms of animal health, there are now techniques for monitoring the health of farm animals with a high degree of accuracy using a camera and AI to achieve a "smart" cow house or poultry house¹².

The early detection of injuries and illnesses that may influence the amount and quality of milk production has been made possible by meticulous observation combined with AI powered image analysis⁴³. Tackling parasites, biosecurity, diseases, and advanced monitoring of farm animals are now possible⁴⁴. Robots are also used to detect oestrus, deliver vaccines, detect avian diseases or nutritional deficiencies in chicks, and detect behavioural diseases like cannibalism (or aggressive pecking)⁴⁵.

10. Traceability and Supply Chain Management – Block Chain Technology

It is common knowledge that individuals are becoming more curious about their food's origins and production processes. Enhancing transparency and traceability through AI in food supply chains (FSC) can help address food safety, quality, and waste⁴⁶. There have been successful experiences integrating blockchain

with AI techniques for product traceability improvement. A blockchain enables food safety and traceability by linking every link in the supply chain, from producer to consume. Providing this information to consumers will become a competitive advantage in the agriculture and food industries¹².

11. Farm Management: Optimisation of Farming Operations and Decisions

To increase farm productivity and reduce risks from weeds, pests, and illnesses, farmers can now adopt a data driven approach by gathering and analyzing vast volumes of data about the current state of their fields. This is made possible by the introduction of new technological trends like AI. Cognitive solutions recommend the best crops and hybrid seeds based on various factors, including soil type, weather, pest levels in a particular area, and seed type¹². Digital technologies used for precision farming gather data from farmers and public data sources evaluated by algorithms and provide the inputs to aid production and increase the farmer's return on investment.

12. Finding Market Opportunities for Farmers

AI-enabled platforms can give smallholder farmers the information they need to connect directly to buyers of their produce, reducing food waste and increasing farm income. AI can also help address market failures by improving traceability to prove the origin and quality of produce, which is needed to secure supply contracts and access markets¹². The role AI plays in the agricultural sector must be considered. The impact of AI on in-farm includes generating diverse data, analysing hyperdata, and making complex and accurate decisions; smart farm management; optimising risk management on farms; and Reducing production costs. The impact is not limited to what happens on the far side alone; it also contributes to off-farm operations. These areas include quality control of food products, optimisation of the food supply chain, optimisation of the packaging process, prediction of market trends, reduction of food waste, and increase in consumer utility⁴⁷. The diagrams below capture the usage of AI in the agricultural sector.

Figure 1: AI models in agriculture⁴⁸.

Figure 2: IOT Smart Plant Monitoring⁴⁸.

Figure 3: Using a Drone to apply fertiliser

Figure 4: Irrigation with IoT².

Although AI implementation varies across nations, it is still in the initial phase in developing countries like Nigeria⁴⁹. Challenges such as data quality, ignorance, privacy and lack of skilled workforce limit the scope of AI implementation in emerging economies, especially in agriculture. Farmers tend to perceive AI as something that applies only to the digital world. They might need to see how it can help them work the physical land. They can be resistant since they do not know how AI tools are used in real-world situations. New technologies often appear complex and needlessly expensive since solution providers must justify their solutions' benefits and how best to use them. While AI has potential applications, technology companies still have a long way to go before they can assist farmers in adequately implementing it¹².

Agricultural productivity has been seen as a measure of alleviating poverty in the world, especially in developing nations. Many studies have linked agricultural productivity to poverty alleviation. Thus, according to the United Nations Development Program (UNDP), agriculture is essential to global economic expansion, the fight against poverty and environmental sustainability. According to a study conducted by the International Food Policy Research Institute (IFPRI), achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), promoting general economic growth, and reducing poverty depend on boosting higher agricultural growth. The goal of achieving zero hunger by 2030 is one of the SDGs⁵⁰. Available evidence suggests that poverty has been a significant problem in Nigeria, even amongst many rural farmers. By implication, AI will boost agriculture, thereby contributing to the well-being of some of these farmers, thereby alleviating poverty. The provision of food and eradication of poverty are benefits of agriculture. Expenditure on agriculture would only reduce poverty if agricultural output is increased. Moreover, one of the ways agricultural outputs could be increased is by deploying AI⁵¹.

AI could play a crucial role in modern-day agriculture¹⁸. By increasing productivity for those involve in agriculture, artificial intelligence can help reduce poverty. According to reports, agriculture significantly reduces poverty particularly for the lowest of the poor; those who make less than \$1 a day. Agriculture has a direct, indirect, and participation impact on farmers and the communities where farming is practiced, which helps to reduce poverty⁵².

Moreover, AI affects agricultural sustainability, management, and productivity of emerging nations. Even though AI has yet to be fully utilised in agriculture, several notable effects have already been observed that

could improve the economy of those involved in agriculture, especially small and medium-scale farmers in rural communities: Increased Productivity and Efficiency; Empowerment of Smallholder Farmers and Sustainable Agriculture Practices⁵³.

Implications for “Agrivangelism”

Some research was carried out in Nigeria about the awareness of AI amongst farmers and extension workers; based on the findings, the majority of farmers who know about and use artificial intelligence-enabled technologies are connected in some way or another to the organisations that provide the services to them. Some randomly selected respondents needed to be made aware of the use of technologies enabled by artificial intelligence⁵⁴.

In such communities, the rural farmers will continue to experience challenges that could further plunge them into further poverty. Many evangelistic outreaches are carried out by poor farmers living in rural settlements. When Jesus was on earth, in the flesh, he carried out His missions mainly in the agrarian communities; hence, most of his parables are rooted in agriculture. While Jesus was doing all these, he reached out to the people holistically; meaning that the church has a responsibility to do the same. Evangelisation should go beyond saving the soul and incorporate the general well-being of the people being evangelised. The following are implications that can be derived from previous discussions in this paper for evangelism by the church and other mission agencies:

1. Holistic Ministry

Evangelism should be a holistic ministry, ministering to the spirit, soul and body. Jesus declared his expectation for holistic evangelism when he stated his mandate in Luke Chapter 4:18-19, "The spirit of the Lord is on me because he has anointed me to proclaim good news to the poor. He has sent me to proclaim freedom for the prisoners and recovery of sight for the blind, to set the oppressed free, to proclaim the year of the Lord's favor." He was quoting from the book of Isaiah 61:1-3:

The Spirit of the Sovereign Lord is on me because the Lord has anointed me to proclaim good news to the poor. He has sent me to bind up the brokenhearted, to proclaim freedom for the captives and release from darkness for the prisoners, to proclaim the year of the Lord's favor and the day of vengeance of our God, to comfort all who mourn, and provide for those who grieve in Zion - to bestow on them a crown of beauty instead of ashes, the oil of joy instead of mourning, and a garment of praise instead of a spirit of despair. They will be called oaks of righteousness, a planting of the Lord for the display of his splendor⁵⁵.

By implication, part of the good news, which evangelism stands for, is to minister holistically to their needs. In this case, poor rural farmers can be ministered to holistically through “agrivangelism” using AI's instrumentality. Jesus further lends credence to this in his parable in Matthew 25:34-46:

Then the King will say to those on his right, 'Come, you who are blessed by my Father; take your inheritance, the kingdom prepared for you since the creation of the world. For I was hungry and you gave me something to eat, I was thirsty and you gave me something to drink, I was a stranger and you invited me in, I needed clothes and you clothed me, I was sick and you looked after me, I was in prison and you came to visit me.' "Then the righteous will answer him, 'Lord, when did we see you hungry and feed you, or thirsty and give you something to drink? When did we see you a stranger and invite you in, or needing clothes and clothe you? When did we see you sick or in prison and go to visit you?' The King will reply, 'Truly I tell you, whatever you did for one of the least of these brothers and sisters of mine, you did for me.' "Then he will say to those on his left, 'Depart from me, you who are cursed, into the eternal fire prepared for the devil and his angels. For I was hungry and you gave me nothing to eat, I was thirsty and you gave me nothing to drink, I was a stranger and you did not invite me in, I needed clothes and you did not clothe me, I was sick and in prison and you

did not look after me.' "They also will answer, 'Lord, when did we see you hungry or thirsty or a stranger or needing clothes or sick or in prison, and did not help you?' He will reply, 'Truly I tell you, whatever you did not do for one of the least of these, you did not do for me.' "Then they will go away to eternal punishment, but the righteous to eternal life⁵⁵.

This is Christ's expectation from every mission agency as they interact with people in different communities with the aim of soul-winning. Jesus exemplifies it in his encounter with Peter and his friends who were into fisheries, which is a branch of the agricultural sector, in Luke 5:1-11:

One day, as Jesus was standing by the Lake of Gennesaret, the people were crowding around him and listening to the word of God. He saw at the water's edge two boats, left there by the fishermen, who were washing their nets. He got into one of the boats, the one belonging to Simon, and asked him to put out a little from shore. Then he sat down and taught the people from the boat. When he had finished speaking, he said to Simon, "Put out into deep water, and let down the nets for a catch." Simon answered, "Master, we've worked hard all night and haven't caught anything. But because you say so, I will let down the nets." When they had done so, they caught such a large number of fish that their nets began to break. So they signaled their partners in the other boat to come and help them, and they came and filled both boats so full that they began to sink. When Simon Peter saw this, he fell at Jesus' knees and said, "Go away from me, Lord; I am a sinful man!" For he and all his companions were astonished at the catch of fish they had taken, and so were James and John, the sons of Zebedee, Simon's partners. Then Jesus said to Simon, "Don't be afraid; from now on you will fish for people." So they pulled their boats up on shore, left everything and followed him⁵⁵.

Jesus entered Peter's boat to evangelise and afterwards divinely helped them because they had been toiling throughout the night and had caught nothing. They would have gone home empty-handed, but they experienced a bountiful harvest by divine intervention. The last part of the text shows that they surrendered everything and followed Jesus. By implication, Jesus helped their vocation to be productive and made them surrender their lives to him; this is what "agrivangelism" represents. Therefore, as people go out for evangelism based on the great commission in Matthew 28:19-20, the poor farmers in the rural communities could be won for Christ through "agrivangelism", hence, it is a divine command.

2. Community Engagement

There is a need for missionary agencies to engage the local farmers in the target communities to understand their challenges in the area of agriculture. People often go with clothes and toiletries to these communities as they share the gospel with them; this could only help for a while. In order to make a lasting impact with the gospel, there is a need to engage with the community on how the mission agencies could help boost their agricultural productivity. Armed with this information, the mission agencies would be able to know which AI technologies are needed in such communities, and support could be raised to address that area of need.

3. Leveraging Human Resources

There are experts within the church on different aspects of Agriculture, including AI, and they should be an integral part of the team, like the integration of Medical Personnel into evangelistic programs that gave rise to medical missions. The early missionaries used the tools of Education and Medicine for Evangelization. "Agrivangelism" should be another aspect of sensitisation and empowerment for these local farmers to win their souls. These professionals can organise Seminars, workshops and other follow-up programs for these farmers that would help them on their farms. This will cater for their livelihood and their families.

4. Partnership with Government or Private Agencies

There are many government agencies in Nigeria that mission agencies can partner with for “agrivangelism”. These agencies include:

ARCN - Agricultural Research Council of Nigeria;
NVRI - National Veterinary Research Institute;
NIOMR - Nigerian Institute for Oceanography and Marine Research;
NIFOR - Nigerian Institute for Oil-Palm Research;
NRCRI- National Root Crops Research Institute;
NIHORT - National Horticultural Research Institute;
CRIN - Cocoa Research Institute of Nigeria;
RRIN - Rubber Research Institute of Nigeria;
NSPRI - The Nigerian Stored Products Research Institute;
NCRI - National Cereals Research Institute;
IAR - Institute for Agricultural Research;
IAR&T - Institute of Agricultural Research & Training;
NAERLS - National Agricultural Extension and Research Liaison Services;
LCRI - Lake Chad Research Institute;
NIFFR - National Institute for Freshwater Fisheries Research;
NAPRI - National Animal Production Research Institute;
NACGRAB - National Center for Genetic Resources & Biotechnology;
FIIRO - Federal Institute Of Industrial Research, Oshodi;
PRODA - Projects Development Institute;
NITR - Nigerian Institute for Trypanosomiasis Research;
FRIN - Forestry Research Institute of Nigeria;
NARICT - National Research Institute for Chemical Technology;
NISER - Nigerian Institute of Social and Economic Research; and
NSPRI – Nigerian Stored Product Research Institute^{56 57}.

Aside the list above, there are also private agrotech companies in Nigeria. The list includes AirSmat Inc, AgriGrow Analytics, AgriConnect, Quick Leap, FarmCrowdy, Hello Tractor, Thrive Agric, Babban Gona, and Farmz2U⁵⁸. Many more companies in the agro-technology (agritech) play an essential role in the agricultural ecosystem. It is an innovative industry that contributes to improved production efficiency, higher yields and more sustainable agro-crops⁵⁸. Mission agencies can partner with government agencies and private agencies in Capacity Building, Data Accessibility and Management, Policy Framework, Farmers' Involvement and Feedback and Tailored Solutions for the needs of the individual agrarian community.

5. Funding

The missionary agencies or churches involved in evangelism can fund some of these technologies needed for “Agrivangelism”. They could fund Digital infrastructure investments, including improved internet connectivity and storage facilities. They could also give financial support and subsidies to farmers to encourage them to adopt AI technology. In the aspect of financing, the mission agencies can work together or communicate with government organisations like the Nigeria Incentive Based Risk Sharing System for Agricultural Lending (NIRSAL), which offers funds for agricultural reasons. The Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) owns NIRSAL, a non-bank financial institution worth US\$ 500 million. It is intended to redefine, quantify, assess, reprice, and share credit risk associated with agribusiness with investors and financiers⁵⁹. NIRSAL was established to promote the flow of affordable capital and investments into the agricultural sector. It specialises in Agribusiness project development, Finance facilitation and Agricultural risk

management. The agency optimises agriculture and agribusiness, integrates agricultural value chains, facilitates finance and investments and manages agricultural risks through innovative models and self-originated Tools, Techniques, Methodologies and Partnerships (TTM&Ps)⁵⁹. The also involve in restoring agricultural value chains by de-risking the agribusiness finance value chain, establishing long-term capacity, and institutionalising incentives for agricultural lending through its five (5) strategic pillars—risk sharing, insurance, technical assistance, incentives, and rating⁵⁹. The mission agencies can create a platform or facilitate such collaboration to help the farmers boost productivity, thereby alleviating poverty.

Conclusion

In order to increase food availability, achieve food security, and reduce poverty, the agricultural sector is crucial. However, because of the difficulties in developing nations in this sector, current technology and expertise will not allow them to boost productivity. A large portion of the agricultural workforce is made up of peasant farmers who struggle to make ends meet and live in rural communities. To raise the productivity of agricultural produce per unit of land and agricultural worker, there is a need to enhance investments in agricultural research and extension programs in developing nations. One of the ways to accomplish this is by utilising AI. Technology transfer from developed to developing nations should be encouraged to promote these processes, close technology gaps, and overcome knowledge barriers. Recall that compared to other economic sectors, agriculture has a far more significant influence on lowering poverty and enhancing food security.

The church and other mission agencies have a role to play in the agricultural sector. Most of the evangelistic efforts in sub-Saharan Africa from these bodies are carried out in rural communities that are predominantly made up of peasant farmers who need to be in tune with the latest technologies that can help boost their productivity and alleviate poverty. The mission agencies should carry out the holistic gospel, ministering to the Spirit, soul and body. They need to engage in evangelism and use the tool of evangelism to reach out to these people. AI is germane to achieve this. The mission agencies must sensitise, collaborate, and fund such laudable technologies to improve the productivity of the people, improve their quality of life and create an avenue to come in contact with Jesus.

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